

CONVERGENT PARALLEL MIXED METHODS STUDY OF EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING IN PHILIPPINE DRAG PERFORMERS

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Convergent Parallel Mixed Methods Study of Emotional Well-Being in Philippine Drag Performers

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Abstract

This convergent parallel mixed-method research aimed to determine the relationship between emotional well-being and personal growth among drag performers in the Philippines. Using snowball sampling, thirty (30) drag performers in Metro Manila were the respondents, whereas, in the qualitative phase, five (5) drag performers were the participants with ages ranging from 18-50 years and an experience of at least six months or more. The results revealed that respondents had an Average Level (3.36) of Emotional Well-being and a Very High (5.31) level of Personal Growth. There was no significant relationship ($r=-.032$, $p=.867$) between emotional well-being and personal growth among drag performers. Using semi-structured interview guide questions, the qualitative phase generated eight (8) themes, namely: Feeling Welcomed and Accepted; Mockery and Sexism; Emotional Distancing; Escape and Optimism; Passion and Purpose of Being a Drag Queen; Financial and Professional Challenges; Confidence Building; and Learning New Skills and Self-Acceptance. The integration phase revealed that because of social expectations and misconceptions about their art form, they frequently encountered prejudice and judgment. However, their passion for drag kept them going, fostering a stronger sense of resilience and self-acceptance. Certain performers have distinct coping strategies, as creative expression in the form of dance, makeup, and costume creation serves as a crucial coping mechanism. Emotional distancing and escape are two strategies in which performers remove themselves from uncomfortable circumstances. Furthermore, humor and optimism are important defense strategies against discrimination and mockery. The function of peer and community support, which provides strong, encouraging networks, is frequently emphasized within the drag community. The study's goal was to raise awareness of the emotional difficulties drag performers experience and the positive aspects of drag in their lives, ultimately providing actionable recommendations to help improve their overall well-being. The title of the proposed program is "Unapologetic Voices: Empowering Drag Performers."

Keywords: *emotional well-being, personal growth, drag performers, convergent parallel, mixed method*

Introduction

Drag shows become increasingly recognized around the world as significant and genuine forms of creative expression. Despite the mainstream exposure drag culture has received, drag performers continue to face discrimination, criticism, and social pressure that negatively influences their emotional well-being. Some countries such as Tennessee, Texas, and Montana pass laws specifically to ban drag performers from performing as they prohibit acts of sexually oriented performances as they are still holding on to conservative beliefs. Drag performances, which question conventional gender norms, face social rejection as an outcome of their resistance. Drag performers may have experienced emotional distress as a result of these difficulties.

Moreover, when such factors obstruct one's ability to express oneself and explore who they are, it could hinder one's personal growth. Among the benefits of drag include acquiring a variety of artistic abilities, such as dancing, fashion, makeup creativity, lip sync, and performances, which encourage people to see drag as a genuine and intricate art form that promotes personal growth. In a setting that does not necessarily support inclusion, drag performers find it difficult to establish an authentic sense of identity and confidence in themselves.

Furthermore, families put pressure on drag performers to fit into traditional roles and comply with societal standards, as they find it difficult to appreciate the creative outlet and significance of drag. The cultural relevance and creative expression that come from drag performances are often left unrecognized by people who have little knowledge of drag as a form of entertainment and art. Drag performers face disapproval from family members, resulting in strained relationships.

Furthermore, Vochelet (2023) mentioned that Pura Luka Vega, a drag performer from the Philippines, was taken into custody on October 4 after portraying Jesus Christ and singing a rock version of the Lord's Prayer late July. The artist was declared "persona non grata" in numerous cities after the post went viral, leading numerous Catholic organizations nationwide to file complaints against him for "desecrating their religious faith and patronage." As the controversy escalated, clubs decided to postpone the artist's scheduled performances. Conservative organizations have traditionally promoted the upholding of moral principles and the conservative Catholic family.

Additionally, drag performers in the Philippines faced a wide range of challenges caused by gender expectations, and social, and cultural factors. They were frequently subjected to stigma as a consequence of the strongly held religious and cultural views that characterized Philippine society. Gender stereotypes and expectations from society cause some people to show opposition towards non-conforming gender expressions. Given that performers challenged conventional gender expectations, this stigma emerged as criticism, rejection, and discrimination. While other countries had come to accept this kind of art, the Philippines remained blinded by

conservative beliefs.

Moreover, due to discrimination, stigma and social rejection, drag performers frequently experience emotional and social difficulties, especially in conservative nations. Many performers develop a diverse coping strategy to deal with the demands of non-conforming gender expression because these difficulties these can have a substantial impact on their emotional well-being and personal growth. Drag is a strong means of resiliency and survival, even if it is frequently viewed as an outrageous form of artistic expression. Performers use a range of ways to cope with the psychological effects of social rejection, such as establishing close bonds with their community in the LGBTQ+ community, confronting adversity with comedy and satire on their performances, and finding comfort in their craft. These coping strategies not only allow them to thrive in the face of discrimination but also contribute to their personal growth and emotional well-being.

Drag performers faced discrimination due to wider stigmas directed towards the LGBTQ+ community, since drag performers happened to be associated with a variety of gender expressions. These issues were made more difficult by online harassment, as social media platforms served as venues for discriminating remarks and unfavorable actions. Negative views stemmed from both generalized stigmas towards the LGBTQ+ community and inadequate or stereotyped portrayals of drag in the majority of media outlets.

Indeed, drag performers often experience pressure from society to follow gender norms, which results in both emotional and personal difficulties. Drag performers also lead in the fight to oppose strongly held prejudices and promote a broader awareness and appreciation of various gender identities as well as representations in society. An emotional battle for acceptance, as well as belonging, could lead to conflict between one's sense of self and expectations, which caused significant distress. Support networks are important to offer an environment of compassion that builds resiliency and lessens the psychological implications.

The primary goal of the study was to gain insight into the relationship between emotional well-being and the personal growth of drag performers. As a result, it was vital to study the drag performers' emotional well-being and personal growth to address the mental health issues and promote personal growth and inclusion of the marginalized community as well as the positive coping mechanisms utilized by drag performers. Also, specialized mental health services for drag performers were to be created, collaboration with LGBTQ+ mental health professionals was to be sought, readily accessible services were to be offered, educational events for the drag community were to be organized, an atmosphere of artistic expression was to be fostered, and emotional health and personal development were to be promoted.

Additionally, the study aimed to shed light on the processes by which drag performance established emotional well-being and personal growth as an individual. Since there hadn't been much research done on drag performers' perspectives in terms of their emotional well-being and personal growth. This study explored an important gap in the current state of data and offered insightful information about the experiences of an underprivileged and marginalized minority.

This study can contribute something to the world of literature, to the lives of drag performers, and to those who are planning to embrace the world of drag performing.

Research Objectives

The main purpose of this convergent mixed methods design was to determine the level of emotional well-being and level of personal growth among drag performers in the Philippines as to the discrimination and prejudice as well as their lived experience. Specifically, the study aims to accomplish the following objectives:

1. Determine the overall level of emotional well-being of drag performers.
2. Determine the overall personal growth among drag performers.
3. Determine the significant relationship between the emotional well-being and personal growth of drag performers.
4. Explore the lived experiences of drag performers as to emotional well-being and personal growth.
5. Integrate the results of the quantitative phase and qualitative phase.
6. Propose a program for drag performers.

Methodology

Participants

The respondents of the study were thirty (30) drag performers for the quantitative part, residing in Metro Manila who had prior participation in doing drag limited to respondents that were part of the LGBTQ+ community with ages ranging from 18 years old to 50 years old. With an experience of at least six months or more which had given them invaluable insight into the field of drag.

In addition, the study was limited to LGBTQ+ as the focus of the study was on the emotional well-being and personal growth of drag performers who were marginalized in the community.

Therefore, this study was made to prove that drag performers are really in need of social support as a potential protective factor against the coping issues that come with challenges from discrimination.

YEARS PERFORMING	FREQUENCY
6 months – 1 year	11
1 ½ year – 3 years	11
4 years – 8 years	5
10 years to 15 years	3
TOTAL	30

The participants of the study were five (5) drag performers for the qualitative part who are residing in Metro Manila. These were drag performers who had prior participation in drag performances. Moreover, the researcher limited the participants who were part of the LGBTQ+ community.

Participants	Age	Year Performing
Participant 1	40	15
Participant 2	24	3
Participant 3	34	7
Participant 4	36	3
Participant 5	30	14

Instrument

An interview and a survey questionnaire were employed as research tools in this study. The questionnaire was a data collection instrument for the study. It was the most utilized method in this type of study. The questionnaire utilized in this study was adopted questionnaires.

An emotional well-being-related question was adopted from The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) which was first created by researchers Watson and Tellegen (1988, as cited in Riopel, 2019). According to Riopel (2019), The Positive and Negative Affect Scale (PANAS) was a psychometric instrument employed for assessing positive and negative affect across particular characteristics. Participants utilized the PANAS to determine what they were feeling and provide input using a survey consisting of 20 items. The responses were then scored using a 5-point Likert scale, where lower scores indicate lower levels of Positive/Negative Affect, and higher scores indicate higher levels. The PANAS had an exceptionally high internal reliability that is consistent with Cronbach alpha coefficient results ranging from 0.86 to 0.90 for the Positive Affect Scale and 0.84 to 0.87 for the Negative Affect Scale.

The personal growth questionnaire was adopted from Ryff's Psychological Well Being Scale it was created by Ryff (2019, as cited in De-Juanas et al., 2020). It was a set of indicators that aligned with an understanding of life satisfaction by utilizing the concept of positive psychological functioning. It was a 42-item self-report tool that measures six aspects of psychological well-being: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self. These aspects addressed the various ways in which people can control their own actions, embrace their own constraints while remaining optimistic, and create meaning and purpose in their own lives. However, the study focused on personal growth and utilized the 7-item self-report on personal growth. A 6-point Likert scale, with 1 indicating "strongly disagree" and 6 representing "strongly agree," was used to rate the items. As a result, the overall score falls between 18 to 108, where higher numbers indicate better well-being.

The research's instruments were able to capture the complex aspects of emotional discomfort personal development, and resilience in marginalized environments. The impacts of discrimination and identity expression, which are major facets of a drag performer's life, were evaluated using the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS), which measures emotional well-being. The Ryff Psychological Well-being Scales, which take into account autonomy, personal development, and self-acceptance, are especially suitable since they measure how drag artists deal with social rejection and self-expression.

The structures of the questionnaires were designed in this manner except for the demographic questions. The first column of questionnaires about emotional well-being was composed of questions and the other five columns were the rating scales ranging from 5-Extremely; 4-Quite a bit; 3-Moderately; 2-A little; 1-Very slightly or not at all. To measure the level of personal growth of the respondents, questionnaires are also prepared. The first column was composed of questions about personal growth and the next six columns are composed of rating scales from 1- strongly disagree to 6-strongly agree.

The questionnaires were to be translated into a Google form for the online gathering of data aligned with the safety precautions. Also, face-to-face interaction or virtual meetings were utilized.

For the interview phase, researcher-made questions are being utilized. Interview Guide Questions:

1. How did you feel when you first shared your passion for drag performance with your family and friends? How did they first react?
2. What experiences of discrimination or prejudice have you encountered as a drag performer?
3. How do you cope with discrimination and criticism? What coping strategies have you used?

4. What keeps you going as a drag queen despite criticism/discrimination?
5. What are the challenges you have faced as a drag performer that helped you grow personally?
6. How does the relationship you have with other performers contribute to your personal growth both professionally and personally?
7. Despite societal pressure, how do you improve as to personal growth or your craft?

Procedure

The quantitative phase involved the administration of the adopted tests on the target respondents. The qualitative phase consisted of eight main questions with follow up sub-questions, designed to ensure sufficient data extraction from selected drag performers in the Philippines. The specific steps of data gathering in this phase were outlined below: The drag performers in the Philippines were researched, and the necessary number of participants was determined. Then, she sent a formal letter to the authors of the standardized questionnaires to which the researcher-made questionnaire was adopted. Snowball sampling helped collect data coming from friends, family members, relatives, and referrals from drag performers.

The first step in the snowball sampling process consisted of selecting key participants who had become well-connected in the drag scene. To make sure that they had wide networks of other performers, these original participants were selected based on their prominence and influential status in the local drag scene. They have to be actively involved in drag performance for at least six months and live in Metro Manila, one of the most well-known drag performance venues in the nation, in order to be chosen.

Following how they are recognized, these original participants were encouraged to suggest additional drag performers who fit the same requirements, so the sample grew naturally. Through the use of personal networks and reliable recommendations, this approach was able to connect with performers who might not have been easily reached by traditional recruitment methods. Making sure that the sample was representative of the larger drag community, the research aimed to incorporate performers with a variety of backgrounds, ages, and experiences in order to reduce bias and increase diversity.

To further enhance transparency, the researcher also kept detailed records of the referral process and the methods used to get in touch with new individuals. All individuals discussed were reminded that participation was entirely optional and that they might withdraw at any time. This approach preserved the participants' anonymity and promoted participation in a secure and welcoming way, enabling the study to collect a representative and varied sample of drag performers.

The identified respondents were oriented on the aims of the study. The consent form was presented first to the well-known establishment where drag was being held. Also, the consent of drag performers to participate in the study was asked. After that, it conducted individual interviews for the qualitative phase via phone calls and face-to-face interactions. Also, the adopted tests based on The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) and Ryff's Psychological Well-Being Scale were administered through Google Forms and face-to-face interactions while following health protocols.

Aware of the risks associated with conducting this study during a pandemic in the new normalcy, as well as the possibility of infection with the COVID-19 virus, precautions were taken to ensure the safety of all respondents. Adherence to all health protocols established by the government was maintained during this time. Conducting face-to-face surveys helped in keeping respondents focused, which improved the results.

Interviews were done both face-to-face and virtually during the data gathering procedure, and each technique had an effect on the quality of the responses. Participants were given the freedom to participate from the comfort of their own homes through the use of online platforms such as Zoom and Google Forms for the virtual data collecting. A sense of security and privacy may have been enhanced by this setting, which may have encouraged more honest and open responses, particularly when talking about sensitive topics like prejudice and social rejection. However, the personal connection of in-person encounters can occasionally be lost in virtual communication, which may limit the depth of responses and non-verbal cues that enhance qualitative data.

On the other hand, face-to-face interviews made it possible for the researcher and participants to have a more personal connection. The researcher was able to observe emotional reactions and body language throughout the face-to-face conversation, which gave the spoken responses more depth. Because they were more involved in a structured interview environment, it also helped keep the participants' attention, which might have improved the quality and comprehensiveness of their answers. However, conducting in-person interviews during the pandemic necessitated rigorous adherence to health protocols, including as wearing of face mask and social distancing.

The research was able to remain flexible during the pandemic by combining virtual and face-to-face methods, which ensured participant safety while collecting thorough data. Each method made a distinct contribution to the quality of the responses, with virtual methods offering comfort and convenience and face-to-face interactions offering richer engagement.

Ethical Considerations

Anonymity, confidentiality, signing an informed consent form, authorization to conduct the study, and voluntary involvement while conducting this study were ensured. Participants' identities were kept private throughout, and no identifiable information about them was disclosed in any communication or written output from the study. Participants' responses were kept confidential because they were

only used for research purposes and could not be accessed directly by anyone who was not involved in the study. The privacy rights of participants were respected by obtaining prior permission before conducting the study.

Strict ethical guidelines were followed, and participants' right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or repercussion was emphasized. Such a concept was explained to all participants prior to data collection, guaranteeing that their participation was completely voluntary. This strategy fostered an environment of trust and respect, giving participants a sense of empowerment and control throughout the research process. By protecting their autonomy, the study upheld high ethical standards, putting the comfort and well-being of all participants first.

In addition, potential research participants were informed about the study's methods and dangers. Finally, informants were not compelled to take part in the research. They had complete freedom in responding to the questionnaire and were able to withdraw from the study at any moment without penalty.

Results and Discussion

This section covers the findings and analysis of the collected quantitative and qualitative data. To derive findings, conclusions, suggestions, and a recommended program from this study, the data were analyzed and interpreted.

Purpose Statement 1: Determine the overall level of emotional well-being of drag performers.

Table 1. *Level of the Emotional Well-being of Drag Performers in the Philippines*

Indicators of Emotional Well-being (Positive Affect)	Mean	SD	VI
1. Proud	4.80	.41	Very High
2. Inspired	4.63	.67	Very High
3. Determined	4.47	.73	Very High
4. Enthusiastic	4.47	.68	Very High
5. Active	4.40	.72	Very High
6. Interested	4.37	.93	Very High
7. Excited	4.30	.88	Very High
8. Attentive	4.20	.71	Very High
9. Strong	4.03	.96	High
10. Alert	3.67	1.21	Moderate
Overall Positive Well-Being	4.33	.40	Very High
Indicators of Emotional Well-being (Negative Affect)			
11. Distressed	3.17	.91	Moderate
12. Nervous	2.87	1.07	Moderate
13. Jittery	2.80	.89	Moderate
14. Scared	2.43	1.10	Low
15. Upset	2.40	1.00	Low
16. Irritable	2.20	1.10	Low
17. Afraid	2.17	1.02	Low
18. Hostile	2.10	.89	Low
19. Guilty	2.03	.96	Low
20. Ashamed	1.70	.79	Low
Overall Negative Well-Being	2.39	.57	Low
Overall Level of Emotional Well-being of Drag Performers			
Positive Affect	4.33	.40	Very High
Negative Affect	2.39	.57	Low
General Assessment	3.36	.30	Moderate

Legend: 4.20-5.00 = Extremely/Very High | 3.40-4.19 = Quite a Bit/High | 2.60-3.39 = Moderate/Average | 1.80-2.59 = A little/Low | 1.00-1.79 = Very Slightly/Very Low

The overall well-being of drag performers in the Philippines Moderate (Average, 3.36). The positive affect of their emotional well-being was Very High (4.33) while the negative affect was Low (2.39). Furthermore, the indicator "Proud" had the highest computed mean of 4.80 which was verbally interpreted as Extremely or Very High while the indicator "Ashamed" had the lowest computed mean of 1.70 and was interpreted as A little or Low.

The study highlights that positive affect, such feeling "proud," "inspired," and "determined," are crucial for everyday resilience in addition to being markers of emotional well-being. These feelings undoubtedly encourage performers to more fully accept who they are, bravely confront societal challenges, and boost their motivation and self-esteem. It appears that the performers' satisfaction and love for what they do influence their encounters, promoting a circle of social empowerment and self-acceptance. Performers who are proud of their work may find it easier to deal with social pressure and outside criticism, allowing them to succeed on and off stage.

On the other hand, negative affects like anxiety, fear, or discomfort are generally reported at relatively low levels, but they certainly still have a significant influence on performers' everyday lives and psychological well-being. Greater susceptibility to anxiety could represent a symptom of ongoing distress, especially in a culture that may not always embrace or encourage their profession

Drag offers a platform for genuine, artistic self-expression. Drag performers frequently take great satisfaction in their creative skills and performances. It allows individuals to create characters that inspire courage, confidence, and beauty in them which makes them

proud as performers.

As stated by Joplin (2023), in recent years, the Philippines drag culture had double advantages as "Drag Race: Philippines" and "Drag Den" had both debuted, elevating the visibility and possibilities of local queens. Manila Luzon was thrilled that both programs were running and showcasing various facets of the nation's drag culture. She claimed that growing up, she did not have many Asian role models or sources of inspiration, much less gay Asian ones. For this reason, she thought it would be great to be on a reality show where she met genuine people and observed how it had encouraged many more Asian and gay Americans to be open and proud of their identities.

In relevance to the Intersectionality theory of Crenshaw (2019, as cited in Lockwood, 2023), that the idea to describe the intricate interactions between many forms of prejudice, especially when it involves communities that are marginalized. It indicated diverse dimensions of prejudice and marginalization in a community where individuals with complex racial, gender, or sexual identities may encounter discrimination through various means it was indeed that the drag performers encountered discrimination from the society. However, with the accumulated data it can be perceived how drag positively affects the lives of the performers specifically their emotional-being. In doing their passion for entailing stories artistically helped them find their footing in society. Also, to have an opportunity to showcase their talent was something that made them proud and loud to expose what they got and who they were.

Adding to Crenshaw's idea of intersectionality, several identities including gender, sexual orientation, and socioreligious context causes drag performers in the Philippines to endure multiple levels of discrimination. Intersectionality demonstrates how these intersecting identities, in conjunction with social discrimination, have a particular impact on drag artists' life within the Filipino cultural setting.

Drag performers are frequently stigmatized in the Philippines, where religious conservatism is a significant factor, due to ingrained gender stereotypes as well as their affiliation with the LGBTQ+ community. According to the survey, conservative religious groups frequently support conventional gender norms, and the majority of Filipinos identify as Roman Catholic. In the Philippines, drag performers who defy social standards by exhibiting gender fluidity and nonconformity are subjected to discrimination, which is made worse by this religious influence. Additionally, intersectionality highlights the social constraints drag performers encounter from inside their own communities. A further important aspect of marginalization is family rejection as a result of non-conforming sexual identities and gender expression. Due to a lack of family support, many drag performers struggle with their identities, and emotional distress. Furthermore, misconceptions promoted by the media significantly marginalize these performers through public prejudice and online harassment. This accentuates how their personal and professional identities are impacted by the intersectionality of societal discrimination from several sectors, including the media, family, and religion.

Additionally, Olsen (2023) mentioned that renowned drag artists were frequently featured in the media, greatly enhancing the LGBTQ+ community's exposure. This form of expression continued to play a crucial role in the development of LGBTQ+ culture and history by providing a welcoming space where individuals could express themselves truthfully and be embraced for who they were. Drag became more widely recognized and appreciated as a powerful tool for advocacy, personal development, and expression. Through the artistic qualities of their work, drag was often used by queer artists as an effective way to handle challenging subjects and influence the cultural perceptions of queerness.

It was determined that the majority of those who responded that they were ashamed were drag performers who were rejected by their families and society because of their artistic expression or their profession and for their sexuality. Many drag performers' problems were related to a lack of acceptance and support, and in many cases were being harassed publicly such as catcalling especially when they were already in their drag persona character. As a result of these experiences, it affected their emotions negatively and hindered them from fully reaching their best potential as a drag performer since the feeling of shame swayed them to question themselves. As stated by Ballantine (2021), at its fundamental level, shame was the mechanism by which stigma functioned. When the experience was completely expressed, it might even lead to a damaged identity and promote social marginalization.

According to Trevor Project (2022), in a past poll, 36% of LGBTQ+ individuals reported experiencing direct danger or assault due to their sexual orientation or gender identity, with 31% attributing it to their sexual preferences. Moreover, 73% of respondents stated they had faced discrimination because of these aspects of their identity. LGBTQ+ individuals were more likely to harm themselves due to mistreatment and stigmatization. Alarming data revealed that 14% of LGBTQ+ adolescents had attempted suicide, and 45% had given it significant thought in the previous year. Additionally, 73% of LGBTQ+ individuals claimed to have experienced anxiety symptoms, and 58% indicated having depressive symptoms. Despite these obstacles, 82% of the population still found it difficult to obtain psychological support; of those who sought it in the previous year, 60% were unsuccessful in getting it.

However, research was scarce on the emotional well-being of drag performers in the Philippines. It may be especially important to learn about drag performers' perceptions of emotional well-being and its sources. As it was proved that gender non-conforming claimed to have a higher level of depressive symptoms than heterosexual people resulted for the discrimination and criticisms towards them.

Purpose Statement 2: Determine the overall level of personal growth of drag performers

The personal growth among drag performers in the Philippines was Very High (5.31, σ -0.45) Furthermore, the indicator "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth." had the highest computed mean of 5.97 which was verbally

interpreted as Very High while the indicator “When I think about it, I haven’t really improved much as a person over the years.” had the lowest computed mean of 4.53 and was interpreted as High. Those that have * indicated that it was reverse scored.

Table 2. *Level of Personal Growth among Drag Performers in the Philippines*

Indicative Statement	Mean	SD	VI
1. For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth.	5.97	.18	Very High
2. I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about yourself and the world.	5.83	.38	Very High
3. I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons. *	5.67	1.00	Very High
4. I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time.	5.50	.68	Very High
5. I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago. *	4.97	1.59	High
6. I do not enjoy being in new situations that require me to change my old familiar ways of doing things. *	4.77	1.10	High
7. When I think about it, I haven't really improved much as a person over the years. *	4.53	1.53	High
Overall Personal Growth	5.31	.45	Very High

Legend: 4.20-5.00 = Extremely/Very High | 3.40-4.19 = Quite a Bit/High | 2.60-3.39 = Moderate/Average | 1.80-2.59 = A little/Low | 1.00-1.79 = Very Slightly/Very Low

Drag performers are concerned about the way they could improve, elevate, and acquire new experiences and learnings to be better at their chosen craft. Hence, improving oneself and their persona can boost their confidence. They are concerned about how to improve their skills when it comes to dancing, lip-syncing, and delivering their performances positively. To fully express themselves without the judgment of society. These are all common concerns and drag performers may experience some or all of them.

The results concerning personal growth across drag performers in the Philippines have important influences for their growth and development. The data collected indicated that drag performers have a high level of personal growth, a strong sense of continues growth and improvements in their lives, with a mean score of 5.31. The indicator "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth" obtained the highest computed mean of 5.97, which is classified as "Very High." This highlighted a passionate confidence among drag performers that life was a journey of continuing improvement, which helped explain why they were resilient and motivated.

On the contrary, the indicator "When I think about it, I haven't really improved much as a person over the years" had the lowest mean score of 4.53, interpreted as "High." It indicated that despite drag performers has experienced intense personal growth, some of them believed they haven't achieved substantial improvements or still have an opportunity for improvement. This study indicates a possible area whereby particular help or interventions might foster these performers' personal growth and satisfaction.

Further elaborating on the personal growth of drag performers, a number of particular experiences showcase their journey of self-awareness and resilience. According to one performer, drag forced them to step outside of their comfort zone and learn new skills like dancing and imitation of their idol celebrities that they had not tried before. Embracing artistic expression through drag and venturing into the unknown lead to personal growth, as demonstrated by this transformation. Another performer highlighted the guidance and encouragement they got from more experienced drag performers. Particularly in areas like makeup and performance strategies, this community helped them hone their skills, emphasizing the value of teamwork and learning from more seasoned drag performers in promoting personal growth. Also, the necessity for flexibility in their craft, where they must constantly adapt to changing audience expectations and emerging trends, was another often-addressed topic by performers. This flexibility is not only a professional competence but also a lesson in resilience and flexibility for life. Performers noted that the high expense of costumes, makeup, and wigs prevented them from fully pursuing their craft, and financial difficulties were also mentioned as a barrier to personal growth. However, performers showed perseverance in the face of these challenges by persistently moving from bar to bar in search of performing opportunities and demonstrating their resolve to keep developing both personally and professionally.

In line with this, the study perceived that the participants have a positive outlook when it comes to their personal growth. They were open to actively exploring more that can contribute to how they can furthermore transform their empowering stories into artistic performances. Besides, it was a great way to delve into their self-discovery by getting to know more about themselves. It agreed with the theory of Ryff's (2019, as cited in Charry et al., 2020), a framework of characteristics that includes satisfying fundamental needs and having pleasant experiences are what make up the multifaceted and dynamic concept of psychological well-being. Psychological Well-being where it pointed out how seeking personal growth impacts life satisfaction and paves the way to finding the purpose of their existence.

Baxter et al. (2022) mentioned that drag was a safe space for people from different backgrounds to gather, celebrate, and interact had been made available by drag events. The acceptance and promotion of drag culture in wider society had grown significantly in the last few years. Formerly an outlet for the LGBTQ+ community to express themselves politically and for recreational purposes, it had evolved into a well-liked community that brought people together for overall well-being and enjoyment. Though they began as discreet

show. Drag queens challenged prejudices and advocated for social change by using their voices to draw awareness to crucial issues. Through this artistic medium, performers defied gender norms and fearlessly and passionately embraced various aspects of their identities. Drag performing provided them with the confidence to be authentic and find inner strength. Drag was considered by many members of the LGBTQ+ community as an essential means of self-expression; for some, it even changed their lives. Drag was an unconventional way to express gender identity, challenging social norms and promoting empowerment. It was not just about growth in oneself. Beyond personal experiences, drag fostered a sense of community and belonging.

Furthermore, Colbert (2023) stated that according to the American Academy of Pediatrics, in contrast to their heterosexual counterparts, people who identified as transgender or gender-nonconforming experienced higher levels of anxiety and depression. The negative perception associated with drag had negative impacts on the mental health of drag performers. With its positive aspects drag shows can help people feel less depressed and anxious while also increasing crowd satisfaction and psychological well-being, according to research conducted by UK academics.

High levels of depression were found in this community, according to a study by Knutson et al. (2019). The goal of this latest study was to learn more about these mental health issues and the potential contributing factors. These findings highlighted the importance of improving the mental healthcare of drag performers, particularly in circumstances such as assault in public places, discrimination, and online harassment, as these can lead to increased stress, and depression symptoms, which can have negative consequences on their overall well-being.

Purpose Statement 4: Explore the lived experiences of drag performers as to emotional well-being and personal growth

Feeling Welcomed and Accepted

It was a big step for the drag performers to finally open up to their immediate family, friends, and other loved ones about their passion for drag performance. Coming out has been a struggle for them due to fear of rejection and anxiousness from the possible reaction of their loved ones. This theme of Feeling Welcomed and Accepted was generated from the answers of the respondents, it includes their experiences of how their family opens up their minds to their passion and supports them.

Considering their family background has been also a huge factor to the built up of fear that the respondents felt on revealing their passion for drag performance as this was evident to the garnered data. As a subtheme, Fearful to come-out but eventually being accepted this highlighted how family background really played a crucial part in the decision of the respondent to come out. This was proven from the statement of P5, “I have this fear na baka hindi nila matanggap yung ginagawa ko, kasi nanggaling kase ako sa pamilya na medyo masculine yung mga tito ko. So, basically, parang siyempre, pag nanggaling ka sa ganung pamilya, talagang matatakot ka mag-out pag ganung eksena.”

In relevance to this, the subtheme Depressive-feelings, stressed and pressured exposed their negative feelings when they come out, especially the weight they carry on their shoulders. This was shared by P2, “nagpalaki saken kase I was raised by a pastor. Well, being of course, nakaka-depress, nakaka-stress kase syempre pressured ka and most especially na ako yung panganay na lalaki sa family which they really treasured as a Muslim”.

But mustering their courage to be finally true within themselves also helps their family to open their hearts and appreciate their passion for drag performance. This was apparent to the subtheme, Feelings of Appreciation, Support, and Surprised Reaction coming from the family, it shows how their parents slowly acknowledge them. P1 stated that, “nagulat sila to be honest nanggaling ako sa conservative family... unti unti nyang na appreciate natatanggap yung ginagawa ko as a performer and proud sya sa mga kaibigan nya kunyare sa bahay may bisita pag lumalabas ako nan aka make up ako nahihiya ako minsan tapos sya pa yung nagpapatawag saken sasabihin nya “lumabas ka nga papakilala kita sa mga kaibigan ko, parang ayan lumalabas yan sa GMA” “. and also added, “I feel like they supported me because most of my friends are part of the community.”

Moreover, the Understood by family and circle of friends, feeling respected subtheme explores how some respondents didn't struggle that much as their family openly embraced their passion. This was strongly evident from the experience of P3, “I guess where people, like, in my closest, you know, circle of friends and in my family naintindihan nila. So, wala naman problema within my family and my friends.” and by taking pride to their craft, “As a breadwinner, parang there's some sort of respect to what I do as a performer.” Similarly, the Supportive Family and Friends subtheme received recognition since the beginning of their career, as P4 shared, “Actually my mother is supportive even when I was doing pageant way back in 2010. Yeah, all of my friends and all of my circle are really supportive when it comes to me doing the things that I wanna do in life.”

Drag performances can be challenging at times, particularly when one has to cope with discrimination and rejection because of their artistic expression. Drag performers can overcome these difficulties efficiently if they have an emotional support system of family and friends who are there for them when things become tough. Additionally, having someone who recognizes and embraces their uniqueness and their passion for drag gives them essential validation and enhances their self-confidence. Also, performers are able to openly accept and embrace their creative outlet without being afraid of criticism. As a result, family and friends' understanding and support are crucial for drag performers to succeed in their chosen craft.

Interview Question 2. What experiences of discrimination or prejudice have you encountered as a drag performer?

Theme B Mockery and Sexism

The themes of Mockery and Sexism emerged through the responses of drag performers from their experiences of discrimination based on their identity and their way of expression. In addition, they do not conform to the traditional norms, and that is why some tend to mock them. It has not been easy for them to just always accept all the judgment and mockery that has been thrown at them. This includes their never-ending encounters with catcalling as well as the rejection they must deal with due to religious prejudice.

Some people are less educated and clueless about what drag is. The subtheme, Being Mocked, Sexism demonstrates how people make fun of the drag performers as well as calling them names that make them uneasy especially when they are wearing their costumes. For instance, P4 shared “Sometimes, most of the discrimination that I’ve experienced, I was catcalled, especially when the queens are going to their gigs na naka ayos na from their respective homes. So, syempre sa labas magugulat ung mga tao, hindi naman lahat ng tao sa Pilipinas ay knowledgeable and educated when it comes to doing drag.” and added, “Ahh, bakla ka? Uh, ano ba. Pero not in a good way, “Huy bakla.” pero kunware nakangiti pero if it’s something like rude or in a bad manner that people are gonna call you “bakla” or maybe something like uh “Psst” that’s also a form of harassment.” This was supported by the statement of P1, “And yung tolerance sa mga LGBT community syempre medyo ano pa sila tutuksuhin kami “bakla, bakla, salot, salot” ganun so nung nag sisimula ako ang daming ganyan. Syempre naglalakad kame sa kalye minsan naka costume andun pa din yung tutuksuhin ka “bading, bakla, salot”. And P2 shared the impact of such discriminations, “minsan nakaka-apekto sa mental health naten like yung parang “salot kase bakla” ganyan or parang may hindi magandang gagawin when you are with some straight guys kase parang laging ang iisipin nila is may gagawin kang hindi maganda for them. So, that’s why I have also become an advocate of Sogie Bill. Kase parang yun, yun lang yung isa nating last will na lang para kahit papano maiwasan natin yung cat calling.” With their responses, it has been strongly evident that even though society has been slowly accepting the LGBTQ community there are still people out there that refuse to open their minds and offer respect to the drag performers.

Religious Discrimination and Sexism. This another subtheme entails the judgment that the drag performers received as they were being discriminated against from the religious beliefs that the people were claiming against them. Until now, there was still a strong belief that if they are a queer they are already sinful, and it is unacceptable in the religion’s perspective. This was experienced by P3, “I grew up Catholic pero kahit matindi ang paniniwala ko sa isang diyos mayroon parin magsasabi sa’yo na “ang kabaklaan ay isang kasalanan... na mapupunta ka sa impyerno...” I grew up in that. Iyon kasi ang usually na nakikita ng tao kesyo bakla, parang feeling nila makasalanan na agad.” and he also encountered how some people used the teachings of bible to justify their claim, “From our experience; experience growing up as a queer person, madalas kaming makakarinig ng mga tao or sa mga tao na ginagamit ang bibliya as a weapon against us.” In addition, this was similar to the statement of P5, “Isa rin sa mga pinakamalaking discrimination din na nangyayari yung mga religious people na tinitignan pa rin nila yung kabaklaan as something na hindi maganda, na hindi daw kame makakapasok sa langit.” and he shared his sentiments, “Ayun isa rin sa mga discrimination na parang, tipong, why do you have to justify your religion, your thinking, your belief, eh, sa religion namin, sa simbhang katoliko? Wala nang sinasabi yung Santo Papa sa amin eh, bakit yung pinagpipilitan yung mga bagay na, tsaka isa pa, why do you use the Bible to mock people? diba? Why do you use the Bible to discriminate?”

This clearly shows that the respondents have been exposed to discrimination and it affects them emotionally and psychologically by being mocked for who they are and placing prejudice that their choice of who they want to be is treated as a sin. And that some people use the Bible to mock their identities.

Also, Kaniuka et al. (2019) stated that the systems in society frequently imposed judgment, discrimination, and strict standards, which led to the marginalization and repression of specific communities, religious beliefs, and sexual orientations. Overall health and well-being suffered as a result. Particularly LGBTQ+ views have experienced restrictions, as well as pervasive violence, hostility, and covert and overt forms of discrimination that harmed marginalized individuals as well as community groups.

According to De Guzman (2022) the Roman Catholic Church, which has more than 1.2 billion devotees worldwide, had a significant impact on legislation, traditions, and everyday life. However, conservative groups who referenced Bible texts and Church publications to defend their inflexible conviction to believe there were only two genders and to declare their opposition to homosexuality have given LGBT individuals in Catholic countries a hard time.

Interview Question 3. How do you cope with discrimination and criticism? What coping strategies have you used?

Theme C Emotional Distancing, Escape, and Optimism

Because of the discrimination that the drag performers encountered, they did do things that can help them how to handle it positively. This theme, Emotional Distancing, Escape, and Optimism includes the ways how they deal with the criticisms from the people around them.

Drag performers were often discriminated against based on their identities, they were catcalled with different names instead of being affected by the negative things that were thrown at them they saw it in a positive outlook rather than as being stressed out. In the subtheme, Diversion it depicts that the respondent decided to just find a distraction and focus on other things despite the encountered judgements. “Ako, ginagawa ko na lang comedy, kase ayokong ma-stress” “ginagawa ko na lang comedy sasabihin ko “ang pangit mo

bakit kita papansinin” alam mo yun parang “mas maganda ako sayo ang pangit mo ikaw pa yung nanunukso”. This was the experience of P1 in handling criticisms. On the other hand, Optimism was another coping mechanism whereas they just stick with their positive outlook that not all people are the same. As P2 believed “minsang gagawin mo na lang is to think of it and then at least to realize the silver linings. Kase diba people are different was born different so parang kung ang treatment sayo ng ibang tao ay ganito hindi naman lahat ganun ang magiging treatment sayo.”

Furthermore, Detachment from situation as a subtheme refers to the coping mechanism wherein, they just isolate themselves away from the situation that makes them uncomfortable or downhearted. “I was able to cope up with it because I have to separate myself from the situation and when I say this ibig sabihin hindi ko pwedeng isipin lang ang sarili ko when I was facing this issue” shared by P3.

Also, Speaking up was when they felt the need to finally break their silence amidst the criticisms and discrimination. As P4 stated, “I actually sometimes have to speak up, speak up for other people for yourself, in my case, if it's something that will cost in my inner peace, and peace of mind, I don't and I will never tolerate or entertain negativity.” In relevance, Shrugging it off and by defending oneself was another way of coping by depending on the circumstances whether to just let things be or address it. This was apparent to the statement of P5, “Minsang dededmahin mo na lang, Ayoko na mag please ng mga tao. Kung baga, parang kung ayaw mo sa akin, edi wag, block na lang kita.” “Minsang there are actually, ah, instances that we have to defend ourselves. We have to at least clarify ourselves na, ah, yung sinasabi mo ay mali. Ang sinasabi mo ay hindi tama.”

Consequently, Del Mundo (2023) mentioned that through their performances, drag queens had become assertive, talented, and humorous people who used their platform to speak out against injustice and oppression. These artistic efforts conveyed an overwhelming desire for freedom and equality. Drag performances, as a creative outlet, have played a major role in defying cultural norms and shaping Philippine culture. These creative expressions were an efficient medium for social observation and were successful in advocacy. Drag queens' uniqueness, bravery, talent, charm, and uninhibited self expression were major factors in the rapid transformation of society.

Interview Question 4. What keeps you going as a drag queen despite criticism/discrimination?

Theme D Passion and Purpose of being a Drag Queen

To entirely understand what drag means to the respondents and what keeps them continuously pursuing it generated the theme, Passion, and Purpose of being a Drag Queen. This uncovers how deep their passion for drag is and how it made them feel fulfilled. At the same time, it paves the way for their personal growth.

Life purpose was a subtheme that pertained to the self-discovery of the respondents to what their purpose in life was and how it was fulfilling on their part to bring happiness to other people through their performances. These were the thoughts shared by P1, “I consider drag kase as my calling sa buhay yun na lang yung iniisip ko .. kapag nakikita ko yung mga audience na natutuwa, namamangha sila” and P4 “I usually sometimes just go on with my own life, and the things that I want to do or love to do,”

Similarly, Life purpose and personal growth were the subthemes that reveal how drag gives meaning to their life. Despite the criticisms they faced when asked what kept them going, P3 responded, “Honestly, people who believe in me. I mean sabi nga ni Lady Gaga "if there are 99 people in the room that don't believe in you and there's only 1 that believe in you." Furthermore, he wanted to reciprocate the appreciation and recognition that the people were extending to him. “There are people who want me to perform, who see me as an investment, they want to support my drag and all of these things and I think I have to honor that. I have to make sure na, kung ano ang binigay nila, maisusukli ko diba? Like, I'm so blessed kasi with people who are show me love and support eh. So I'm like "aww.", So ako, bilang mang-lilikha, I just had to remind myself na there are a lot of people that are looking forward to what I do. So, I might as well give them a good show. Keep on telling these stories that they would appreciate you.” In addition, they have needed to have a strong mindset that they will need to stay firm so people would not be able to say anything against them. P5 believed that “So, I have this mindset that I must have a strong backbone na even though I will encounter such discrimination, I still have to overcome it.... pero if you will act superior and may strong backbone ka for yourself, hindi ka nila malalait.”

Personal Growth was noted also as another subtheme that indicated how drag helped the respondents other than financially but also to grow individually and excel in the career that they were passionate about. This is clear as P2 shared, “Aside from living a life, of course, that is a source of income na already. Of course, that is also my passion...sobrang thankful na lang din that I was being surrounded by a lot of people na nakikita parin yung good side sa lahat ng mga ginagawa mo even magkamali ka man”

In connection with the statements of the respondents, it was noticeable that drag helped them a lot may it be financial or the personal aspects of their life. It helped them to excel in their passion and this suggests that within the drag community, there is a nurturing environment that helps them promote personal growth may it be a personal or professional component of their lives.

Interview Question 5. What are the challenges you have faced as a drag performer that helped you grow personally?

Theme E Financial and Professional Challenges

Financial and Professional Challenges were the theme derived from the constant responses of the five participants based on their

experiences that they have faced as a performer whether financial, in terms of performances or opportunities these factors gave the participants a feeling of discomfort.

Given that drag was very expensive they had to provide extravagant costumes and make-up on their own. Limited resources and opportunities were faced by the participants especially when social media was not that prominent where they had to personally inquire at different bars if they needed a performer.

As a subtheme, in Financial Challenges and Limited Opportunities it can be concluded that drag can be very costly because they have to provide their own costumes, wigs and make-up as they have to maximize the resources that were available for them. Also, drag as a career is not a permanent job as it depends on the availability of the job offers, relative from P1 stated “*unang-una ang financial, financial challenges. Kasi, ang drag talaga is mahal expensive talaga unang una kelangan mo mag provide ng make up, ah costumes, wigs, naging challenge sya for me nung nag s-start ako kase syempre konti pa lang yung kinikita. Hirap kumuha ng performance kase limited lang kung saan pwede mag performers kase hindi naman lahat merong ganung klase ng performances so kelangan mo talaga ng pumunta hindi pa kase uso ang social media noon so ang challenge ko noon kunyare part of Quezon City punta akong Paranaque mag travel doon magtatanong tanong “kung kelangan mo ba ng performers” and this was similar to the experiences of P5 when he stated that “Challenges. I think the biggest challenge na ano ko sa drag performer is actually the budget. Sobrang ano yung budget talaga. Kasi drag is very expensive. And dahil sa budget nga yung problema ko sa pagiging drag queen, kailangan ko i-maximize po anong meron ako eh. Even though yung ginagaya ko, sobrang expensive ng mga outfits and all, sa pinakamalit na budget na meron ako, kailangan ko i-maximize po yan na magmukha pa rin syang the same ng ginagaya ko” it reveals the struggles of drag performers as evidenced by the responses gathered.*

In the second subtheme, Flexibility as a Performer showed that a performer were responsible and capable of easily adapting to the situation depending on the theme of their performance because not being able to adjust from the concept could affect the entire performance relevant to the answer of P2 when he stated “*Recently, we’re actually doing some impersonation which is really not my forte. Parang because of doing impersonation here, parang I was being responsible enough para lang gawin yung mga ganung bagay na feeling ko na hindi ko kayang gawin before.*” showed that he was conscientious as a drag performer despite not being naturally drawn to impersonation still he tried to do his best to give an impressive performance to the audience. Also, he discovered that he had this hidden talent as an impersonator. Furthermore, a performer should be able to adapt and be flexible when needed because they have diverse audiences who will critique their performances as P3 stated “*When you’re working, ano kasi, I’m a regular performer at Nectar Nightclub. So, usually they would specify like, kunwari Ariana night or Lady Gaga night or K-pop parang ganon. Kailangan mong i-adjust yung performance mo sa kung anong klaseng audience meron ka or ano yung tema. Medyo mahirap 'yon actually. Pag drag artist ka usually dapat kontrolado mo 'yon pero yung mga bagay medyo challenge lang pero hindi ibig sabihin na hindi mo kayang gawin. Kaya mo pa rin naman*” showed the necessity to adjust to their performances. Also, this demonstrates the versatility and confidence of the performer despite the unexpected concepts that they need to establish to match with the audience.

Furthermore, Upgrading Drag Costumes and Performance as a subtheme showed drag performers wanted to enhance their costumes and elevate their performances despite the financial struggles since it is their way of expressing themselves and their art as well as showcasing their talents and creativity. Specifically, P4 stated “*I promised myself to elevate all of my drags, change all of my closets stuff. So, right now I started changing all of my costumes into a showgirl type of aesthetic for drag. Like gems, crystals, uh no for basics something like that. Kaya lang, the only consequences is that it’s really expensive, you need to work hard for you to be able to earn money, to spend for your drag stuffs*”

Interview Question 6. How does the relationship you have with other performers contribute to your personal growth both professionally and personally?

Theme F Confidence-Building

The theme Confidence-Building manifested from the responses of drag performers. As seen in the remarks, most of them received invaluable support from the community and mentorship from senior drag performers. Through this mentorship, they can grow, and receive pieces of advice from senior drag queens that can improve their skills and elevate their performances. Through this community, they can express themselves and find a safe space for them.

Supportive community was a subtheme that exhibited the experience of drag performers. As a result of the comforting environment brought by other drag performers that had been established in the community this led to the encouragement to embrace their own identity without fear of being judged. And through the uplifting setting this contributes to drag performers personal growth through their guidance since they have more experience in the field as evident to response of P2, when he stated “*Actually, lahat sila nag cocontribute each of them parang marami akong natututunan sa kanila may mga nakukuha akong bagong ideas, lalo na yung talagang matatagal na sa industry. And then, I was actually looking forward to them. So that’s why, parang yung mga ginagawa nila parang natututunan ko na din gawin and I also applied it para makapag turo rin sa iba. So each of them talaga sobrang daming contribution sa looks, sa make-ups, on how you perform, yung mga ganung bagay yun yung mga natutunan ko sa kanila” also P3 stated “*But we have an understanding kasi of what we do in our role in the community, the role of drag in the community. So, we help each other out. So, when we feel like, you know, one needs an editing for their outfits, like “ate, mas maganda yata kung ito yun ginawa mo” or ganon.**

Makakatulong kasi siya in the performance” showed the supportive nature, positive atmosphere and the inclusivity within the drag community. Moreover, the initiative to help other drag performers to be efficient in their skills and performances, also to establish personal growth in their craft.

In addition, Recognizing the legacy of their senior drag queens as a subtheme demonstrated the respect and preservation of the legacy and the tradition of drag. Since senior drag performers were the ones who led the fight for discrimination and unjust treatment it was just right to give appreciation for their contribution. As evidenced by the response of P1 when he stated “unang unang sinasabi ko sa mga nag sisimula mag drag na dapat irespeto nyo sila kase kung hindi dahil sa mga senior drag queens wala tayong stage na pinag peperforman ngayon sila yung lumaban sa discrimination noon sila yung lumaban para ipakilala yung art naten sila yung nag open ng mga bars para saten kung hindi dahil sa kanila wala” showed the recognition for the involvement of senior drag queens to the revolutionary change and the visibility of drag on this days.

Also, the subtheme Boosts Confidence referred to the responses as the incorporation of drag persona through their unique identity and also their creative costumes and makeup which can elevate their confidence. They also could show their talents and creativity through drag. Additionally, this can help them express their authentic selves as P4 stated “it can have you to boost your confidence and able to improve your persona” it emphasized the inspiring aspect and positive influence that drag has brought about.

Moreover, Guidance Coming from their Senior Drag Queens was a subtheme that emerged from the responses about the support coming from senior drag queens having a great impact on younger drag queens as they have invaluable experiences that could help them in their craft. They also advise in terms of their expertise that could make younger drag queens improve their skills and artistic expression that contributes on their personal growth as P5 stated “I met senior drag queens na sila yung nag-guide sa akin na this is what you should do, this is the right make-up that you should do, this is the right blocking of brows. So, alam mo yun, parang, pag mabait ka sa mga tao, maraming tutulong sa'yo” showed the willingness to help and to guide the younger generations of drag queens.

Interview Question 7. Despite societal pressure, how do you improve as to personal growth or your craft?

Theme G Through Learning New Skills and Self-Acceptance

The theme of Through Learning New Skills and Self-Acceptance emerged from the responses of drag performers despite the discrimination and criticism that others may throw at them still they embrace the transformative effect of drag in their lives. Through the incorporation of their drag persona, they can enhance their confidence, creativity, and artistic expression. To celebrate their unique identity defying the norms and expectations of society. Drag performers acquire self-improvement through collaborative mentorship through other performers which could result in personal growth, could promote professional advancement in the field. They inspire others to embrace their uniqueness and to fight for the stereotypes of the community. They are proof of positivity, as they overcome obstacles and still do their passion for drag despite the negative views of others. Nonetheless, they have an optimistic perspective in life despite the stigma coming from society, they find courage in their creative art.

Embracing oneself was a subtheme that exhibited the experiences of drag performers despite the challenges and the criticism they found strength in their genuineness and resisting society's preconceptions about them. They displayed bravery and courage to accept themselves amid discrimination. For drag performers accepting who they were meant embracing their individuality and their true self as stated by P1 “Pero ngayon parang dedma bahala kayo jan sabihan nyo akong bading wala akong pakialam” showed the courage and determination to accept oneself. Also, Optimism, adapting to change and progress was a subtheme that exhibited the experience of drag performers as they constantly need to adjust to new trends, they become experimental in order to remain in the industry and to captivate diverse audiences. They frequently create and change themselves through the experimentation of make-up and looks also their performances and continually improving in their profession as P2 stated “making sure that I was smiling when I was performing kase yun yung mga bagay na napapansin din ng customer. Dancing skills, I think, and memorization of dance steps. Kase parang with 5 yrs of working in a corporate world, parang feeling ko na tigang na yung utak ko sa pag memorize ng ibang mga bagay kase parang nasanay ako na on the spot kong ginagawa yung mga bagay tyaka parang nasanay akong nakaupo lang parang yung katawan ko hindi na sya sanay mag adapt agad but parang working on progress, yun yung mga bagay na inaalar ko ngayon or parang unti unti ko ng narereceive sa katawan ko to work on my dance steps” revealed the resiliency and the professionalism as a drag performer.

Furthermore, Continuous Self-Improvement and Skills Acquisition, and Embracing Oneself was a subtheme that reflected the commitment and artistic development and to refine their skills. They became more creative on how they can improve their craft and acquire new skills for advancement. Thus, they discovered the talents that they never knew they had within themselves. Through drag they can accept their authenticity and to be comfortable on their own skin as P3 stated “You know what I'm saying? So, I knew na when I was performing siguro a year ago, I wasn't as good as I was now. In fact, I became more experimental now after I did drag then. So, before kasi I didn't know how to match my beard tapos coloring my beard and bleaching it so that it matches my hair, my make-up becomes more better. Ang benchmark ko kasi sa personal development ko is, ano eh the skills that I've kind of acquired in bettering my craft. I got better at communicating with other people or performing. So, it's either, you know, it can go from as lineal as personal development on how to do things better but it can also go as deep as how to communicate with other people better. Iyon mas malalim 'yon. So ayon I got better in doing that. I got better with trying to communicate, I got better how to negotiate, I got better with how to work with other Queens and that's because I get to do with what I'm doing and I get to practice and practice and practice, and continue

to do it and do it and do it.” Exhibited the transformative effect of drag to the lives of drag performers.

In addition, Self-determination was a subtheme that exhibited autonomy and empowerment as they showcased their talent. They were not affected by the pressure coming from other people who might not understand the beauty of drag. They can evolve and authentically embrace themselves through their expression as stated by P4 “I don’t feel any pressure unless, of the winners like, when we’re able to answer the question, I have to calm myself for me to be able to think, for me to be able to answer them.” illustrated the strength and the bravery to show their talent. “Kung nadapa ka ngayon, wala kang ibang gagawin kung hindi tumayo at mag-improve.”

Resilience and Embracing Oneself was also a subtheme that reflected the unwavering determination to just keep on pursuing their career by refusing to be defined by the judgment of other people. Drag performers strived to succeed in their craft and the betterment of their drag journey as stated by P5 “Improve yourself. I know na how to manipulate my career, ah, even without the validation of, you know, people. Kasi at the end of the day, naman kasi, it will, I mean, ikaw pa rin naman yung, tutulong sa sarili mo” showed courage and unapologetically expression of oneself highlighting the consistent determination not relying on the validation of others and appreciating one’s self-worth.

Purpose Statement 5: Integrate the results of the quantitative phase and qualitative phase.

Table 4.1. *Integration Results of Emotional Well-being of Drag Performers in the Philippines*

Quantitative Results		Qualitative Results
Item Indicator	Verbal Interpretation	Themes and Subthemes
Proud	Very High	Feelings of Appreciation, Support, and Surprised Reaction coming from the Family Supportive Family and Friends
Alert	Moderate	Detachment from the Situation Speaking Up
Distressed	Moderate	Shrugging it off and by defending oneself Depressive-feelings, Stressed, and Pressured Religious Discrimination and Sexism Financial Challenges and Limited Opportunities
Ashamed	Low	Being Mocked, Sexism

Drag performers were frequently proud whenever they received validation and support, recognizing their identity and artistic ability from friends and family. Simply the source of satisfaction for a drag performer was the recognition, respect, and encouragement they received from their loved ones, particularly from family, friends, and members of the LGBTQ+ community despite challenges. With this support, they became more confident in celebrating their creative skills and genuinely embracing who they were. Ultimately, it gave them the courage and confidence to follow what they loved with the ability to overcome whatever difficulties they encountered.

As they understand the value of taking care of oneself as well as the significance of keeping oneself apart from potentially stressful situations, drag performers frequently experience elevated alertness. They have become conscious enough to know that it may not be beneficial to focus only on their own emotions. Being a drag performer frequently entails overcoming many different kinds of societal, and personal difficulties, such as prejudice and criticism. Being aware of situations where speaking up is important to defend one’s well-being is another aspect that keeps one alert. One of the drag performers shares experiences about how he decided to disregard criticism and cut ties with those who don’t accept them. By refraining from situations that will not contribute to their well being, they have purposely chosen to put their emotional well-being first. Essentially, being alert to their surroundings is a coping strategy used by drag performers to manage the challenges of their personal and professional lives.

Table 4.2. *Integration Results of Personal Growth of Drag Performers in the Philippines*

Quantitative Result	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Result
Item Indicators	Verbal Interpretation	Themes and Subthemes
For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing and growth	Very High	Flexibility as a Performer Upgrading Drag Costumes and Performance Supportive Community Optimism, Adapting to Change, and Progress Continuous Self-Improvement and Skills Acquisition, and Embracing Oneself
When I think about it, I haven’t really improved much as a person over the years	High	Financial Challenges and Limited Opportunities

The results of the study offered valuable insights into drag performers' perspectives on their personal growth. The highest mean score of 5.97 for the statement "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth" demonstrated that most drag performers strongly supported the concept that life was a constant process of learning, changing, and growth. This highlighted a resilient and optimistic outlook that supported progress in personal growth. Some drag performers, on the other hand, felt that their personal growth hadn't progressed much over the years, as evidenced by the lower mean score of 4.53 for the statement "When I think about it, I haven't really improved much as a person over the years." The assessment stayed across the range to be interpreted as "High," suggesting that there was still a moderate acknowledgment of growth regardless of concerns about personal growth. It's important to note that given the lower mean score, the general assessment score of 5.31 for the same statement was interpreted as "Very High," indicating an overall positive assessment. Such a complex viewpoint raised the possibility that drag performers were aware of the many aspects of personal growth, recognizing that there were areas in need of improvement and the continuous nature of advancement.

Drag performers talked about how drag has driven them to push themselves outside of their comfort zones by taking on new challenges. As they acquired new talents and abilities through dancing and impersonation that they never knew existed.

It highlights adaptability and flexibility of drag performers, as they constantly must adapt their performance to fit with the themes and diverse audiences. It also emphasizes how crucial it is to have the ability to learn with current trends and overcome obstacles. It also explores the process of continuous development in their field. Also, according to some of them, they recognize that their abilities have changed over the years. This correlates to the concept that learning, changing, and growth occur continuously throughout life as it shows how taking chances and stepping beyond of one's comfort zone can result in personal growth. They believe that the path of discovering oneself and growth can be enhanced by accepting new experiences and challenges since it allows them to broaden their horizons and uncover talents, they were unaware of.

Table 4.3. *The Relationship between Emotional Well-being and Personal Growth among Drag Performers in the Philippines*

Quantitative Results	Qualitative Results
There was no significant relationship between Emotional Well-being and Personal Growth	Life Purpose Life Purpose and Personal Growth Personal Growth Boosts Confidence Resilience and Embracing Oneself

The findings implied that emotional well-being and personal growth were not correlated among drag performers. In this setting, emotional instability did not always limit personal growth, as seen by the lack of a substantial relationship found between emotional well-being and personal growth. Furthermore, the study highlighted the wide range and complexity of experiences that existed within the drag performance community. It emphasized how resilient people could be in the face of emotional difficulties and yet achieve personal growth, pointing out relevant strengths and specific coping mechanisms.

Drag gives performers an outlet for encouragement, freedom, and artistic expression. Performers can discover different aspects of themselves through their drag persona. Their emotional well-being is enhanced by their freedom of expression, which promotes confidence and self-exploration. Additionally, the support system significantly helps them by encouraging a sense of acceptance as well as belonging. Their resilience and confidence in themselves are increased when they feel valued for what they do, which makes it easier for them to overcome obstacles and unpleasant experiences.

Furthermore, drag performers also feel validated and accepted when they receive praise and encouragement from the audience, which increases their self-worth and builds emotional resilience. As a result, their support has an equal impact on their personal growth as would their intrinsic motivation. Drag performers establish resilience, which is an important component of emotional well-being, by recognizing their individuality. It also highlights how essential it is to keep striving and develop oneself despite obstacles or negativity. This positive mindset, in which obstacles are seen as chances for development rather than barriers, is evidence of a high feeling of emotional resilience.

Moreover, drag is a transforming path of learning about oneself and empowerment, and their continuous development not only improves their artistic profession but also improves their emotional well-being and personal growth. Therefore, a performer's capacity to effectively handle their profession with resiliency and determination enhances their general well-being and promotes further success and personal growth.

According to Dancing Guide (2023) with the rise of prominent reality TV shows, drag had grown in popularity worldwide. LGBTQ+ individuals used it as a stage to display their skills, resiliency, and ways of coping. For LGBTQ+ individuals, drag remained an effective tool that challenged social norms, encouraged diversity, and motivated people to accept who they were. Excessive movements and gestures were used by drag performers as a medium on which they created stories and expressed their passions. They highlighted individuality, self-expression, and the strength of accepting one's genuine self through their performances. They portrayed stories, feelings, and strong messages of inclusivity and acceptance using dance. People of different genders, origins, and sexual orientations are welcomed in the drag community. For people to discover their true identities and express themselves openly, it offered a secure

environment. It built a feeling of camaraderie among LGBTQ+ people and promoted self-acceptance. Drag showed people that each person deserved to be recognized and embraced for what they were in a world where self-expression was frequently suppressed.

Purpose Statement 6. Propose a program for drag performers.

Based on the responses gathered about drag performers frequently experiencing discrimination and discriminatory behaviors, the proposed workshop self-care practices will be employed for drag performers. This includes different coping strategies to be used and how to manage stress. They can acquire the skills necessary to deal with negative opinions of themselves, become resilient despite difficulties, and promote a positive, self-loving perspective. To aid drag performers control their emotions during performances, lessen worry, and develop awareness, the workshop will provide mindfulness techniques. They will get knowledge on how to apply mindfulness to their everyday activities to foster more calmness and concentration. Participants will have the chance to form relationships with other drag performers during the workshop, which will promote a sense of support and community.

<i>Area of Concern</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Person Involved</i>	<i>Success Indicator</i>
Drag performers often encounter discrimination and criticism directed towards them due to creative expression that greatly affect their well-being.	To provide meaningful and useful activities and worksheets that can help drag performers become more resilient, assertive, and self-empowerment strategies.	RESILIENCE BOOST WORKSHOP Teaching drag performers a selfcare program that specifically focuses on mental health, positive talk through self-compassion, and mindfulness techniques. MENTAL HEALTH TALK Invitation of mental health professionals and advocates as resource speakers to provide a comprehensive seminar for gender sensitivity, gender base harassment, establishing inclusivity, safe spaces for drag.	June 2024 - July 2024	Drag Performer LGBTQ+ Community Mental Health Advocates/ Professionals	80% of the participants will used the provided activities and worksheets.
It has been proven that the lack of knowledge of the community in drag makes them susceptible to discriminatory behaviors, harassment, and criticisms.	To provide a greater understanding of the history and culture of drag their meaningful contribution to the community and the positivity of this creative art. Also, to organize public events to promote equality.	COMMUNITY BASED TRAINING Educating people about the history, culture, and of the importance of drag as a form of art as a self-expression. Sharing of personal stories of drag performers so that they could grasp how acceptance are important for the drag performers most especially as a respect for being part of the LGBTQ+ community.	August 2024 – September 2024	Drag Performer LGBTQ+ Community Family Members Barangay Officials/Citizen Mental Health Advocates/ Professionals	80% of the participants will used the provided trainings. The community will be given greater awareness about the challenges that LGBTQ+ individuals experienced as well as drag performers
Limited opportunities and financial challenges were some of the hurdles drag performers had experienced that could affect their passion for drag.	To help drag performers enhance their skills through making their own costumes reducing the cost, activities and workshops for drag performers. and with the help of senior drag queens to establish the support system coming from mentorship.	WORKSHOP AND ACTIVITIES Helping drag performers through programs and workshops on application of makeup, wardrobe design, and other skills could help performers to produce custom attire at less expense, promoting self-sufficient. Creating social media group for the exchange of resources like cosmetics and costume would lower personal costs and encourage collaborations. MENTORSHIP Drag performers can benefit greatly from the advice, assistance, and motivation of mentors as they encounter the difficulties of their profession and their own growth as individuals.	October 2024 – November 2024	Drag Performer LGBTQ+ Community Mental Health Advocates/ Professionals	80% of the participants will used the provided activities and worksheets.

Also, since some people are not fully aware of drag and its creative expression through the incorporation of heavy and colorful make-up, extravagant costumes, and out of-the-world performances. They are easy to judge those who are not conforming to the gender norms. Through the community-based training people will be able to learn about the historical roots of drag and its value in

transformative culture. Also, the program will tackle the creative expression of drag performers to tell their stories and express their identities. With this, people will be able to deeply appreciate the talents of drag performers. Specifically, this program will go through the experiences of discrimination, judgment, and criticism and promote advocacy to fight against inequality, and societal change through acceptance and inclusivity. This program will raise awareness of the experiences of marginalized communities. In addition, a thorough comprehension of the importance of drag as a creative outlet and a means of artistic expression for the LGBTQ+ community will be imparted to participants in the community-based training. Participants will acquire an understanding of the struggles faced by LGBTQ+ individuals through their own stories. They will learn how important it is to have an inclusive, accepting, and respectful society to foster an empowering drag culture.

In addition to, workshop and activities program will be able to help drag performers to help them acquire skills in make-up application, costumes that they will design on their own, and other skills that will help drag performers lower their expenses as doing drag was expensive that may inhibit their growth. Through this they will be able to improvise and improve their skills. Also, mentorship will be employed through the advice of senior drag queens they will gain and insightful ideas and knowledge that could greatly help them as a performer.

By addressing their mental health, building community, and elevating their voices, the "Living Unapologetically, Kicking Stereotypes, Amplifying Voices" campaign seeks to offer drag artists comprehensive support. Quarterly monitoring with LGBTQ+ mental health professionals will be part of the initiative, giving artists a chance to talk about their emotional health and get specialized advice on overcoming the obstacles of prejudice and social rejection. Support groups will also be set up to provide a secure environment for drag performers to talk about their experiences, network with others, and provide support to one another. Through group resilience, these organizations will empower people by fostering a sense of solidarity and belonging.

Advocacy initiatives highlighting the benefits of drag on resilience and personal development will be launched in an effort to better advance inclusivity and understanding. In addition to raising public knowledge and encouraging acceptance of drag as an art form and a form of self-expression, advertisements like these will seek to refute prejudices. The program will also include art therapy workshops, which will give performers a creative way to process their feelings and experiences. Participants' mental health and personal growth will be enhanced by these courses, which will assist them in transforming their difficulties into artistic expression. By using these diverse strategies, the initiative will support the success of drag performers, their unreserved self-expression, and the advancement of an inclusive society.

Conclusions

Drag performers' emotional well-being was not greatly affected by the discrimination and criticisms as drag helps them express themselves genuinely through their artistic expression which impacts their emotional well-being positively.

It is recommended to provide emergency mental health hotlines dedicated to the LGBTQ+ community, especially for drag performers. During mental health emergencies, these services can offer coping mechanisms, emotional support, and prompt professional consultations. For people who are facing emotional distress due to societal discrimination and stigmatization, the hotline may provide instant assistance.

And that to create drag performers-specific community-based mental health support groups. These groups could provide secure settings where people can talk about their experiences, emotional difficulties, and coping techniques. By encouraging one another, this community support would build resilience and give drag performers a sense of emotional safety and belonging.

To provide workshops on mindfulness, self-compassion, and positive self-affirmation, encourage drag performers and mental health professionals to collaborate. Drag performers can create healthy coping strategies for handling performance-related stress, social expectations, and emotional challenges by mastering emotional regulation techniques.

Provide educational initiatives that inform people and family members about the difficulties experienced by drag performers. These initiatives should support acceptance in families and communities, lessen stigma, and advance inclusivity while enhancing the emotional health of performers.

References

- Alfonseca, K. (2022). Drag Queens refuse to 'hide' amid anti-LGBTQ hate, threats and Colorado Springs shooting. <https://abcnews.go.com/Entertainment/drag-queens-refuse-hide-amid-anti-lgbtq-hate/story?id=94480092>
- Anselmo C., Asaali K. M. (2022). The Beauty of Pinoy Drag. <https://tnbmapua.wixsite.com/thenewbuilder/feature/The-Beauty-of-Pinoy-Drag>
- Ballantine, C. (2021). Imogen Tyler, Stigma: The Machinery of Inequality. *Irish Journal of Sociology*, 29(2), 257-261. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0791603520972554>. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0791603520972554>
- Bass, Sally E., "Drag Participation as a Mechanism for Dealing with Minority Stress in LGBTQIA+ Populations" (2021). Senior Projects Spring 2021. 227. https://digitalcommons.bard.edu/senproj_s2021/227

- Baxter, D., Jones, S., & Leer, C., (2022). AUDIENCE DIVERSITY AND WELL BEING AT UK DRAG EVENTS. https://pure.northampton.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/32582458/Published_Paper_Audience_Diversity_and_Wellbeing_at_UK_Drag_Events.pdf
- Brownfield, J., (2023). Is Drag Therapeutic. <https://www.drjennabrownfield.com/blog/drag-mental-health>
- Cai, D., & Guinto, J., (2023) Pura Luka Vega: Philippine drag queen faces backlash for Jesus Act. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-66541089>
- Charry, C., Goig, R., Sánchez, I. et al. Psychological Well-being and Youth Autonomy: Comparative Analysis of Spain and Colombia (2020) DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.564232 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345496933_Psychological_Well_Being_and_Youth_Autonomy_Comparative_Analysis_of_Spain_and_Colombia/citations
- Celestine, N. Ph. D (2021) The Ryff Scales of Psychological Well-being: Your How-To Guide <https://positivepsychology.com/ryff-scale-psychological-wellbeing/>
- Colbert, J., (2023). Drag shows, drag stars are not a threat to society. <https://cluecho.com/23973/opinion/drag-shows-drag-stars-are-not-a-threat-to-society/>
- Dalde, C., (2022). What we can learn about confidence from the queens of Drag Race PH. <https://nylonmanila.com/what-we-can-learn-from-drag-race-ph-so-far/>
- Dancing Guide (2023). Drag Dancing: A Vibrant Fusion of Performance and Expression. <https://medium.com/@dancingguide/drag-dancing-a-vibrant-fusion-of-performance-and-expression-4381017c487a>
- Baxter, D., Leer, C., Graham, A., (2022). “Dragging up the night: exploring the changing dynamic of audiences at drag events in the UK”. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19407963.2022.2042816>. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/19407963.2022.2042816>
- Dawadi, S., Shrestha, S., & Giri, R. A. (2021). Mixed-Methods Research: A Discussion on its Types, Challenges, and Criticisms. *Journal of Practical Studies in Education*, 2(2), 25-36 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46809/jpse.v2i2.20> <https://oro.open.ac.uk/75449/1/Dawadi%2C%20Shreshta%20and%20Giri%202021.pdf>
- Demmi, L., (2023). Breaking the Stereotype: Why Drag Queens are Not the Enemy. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/breaking-stereotype-why-drag-queens-enemy-lisa-demmi>
- De Ayala, S., (2022). Finding Your Inner Drag: How Drag Culture Helped Form Freedom of Expression For the LGBTQ Community https://scholarcommons.scu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1055&context=e_ngl_176
- De Guzman, C., (2022) In the Philippines, You Can Be Both Openly LGBT and Proudly Catholic. But It’s Not Easy. <https://time.com/6184345/lgbt-philippines-catholic-churchpride/>
- De-Juanas, A., Romero, T.B., Goig, R., (2020) The Relationship Between Psychological Well-being and Autonomy in Young People According to Age doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.559976 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7758206/>
- Del Mundo, Z., (2023). BAKLASin ang Kinagawian: The ever-evolving artistry of Filipino drag performance and queer art. <https://uplbperspective.wordpress.com/2023/07/17/baklasin-ang-kinagawian-the-ever-evolving-artistry-of-filipino-drag-performance-and-queer-art/>
- Del Valle, M., (2020). Your Pitch Needs More Drag: Lessons on Presenting, from Drag Queens <https://medium.com/@marcodelvalle/your-pitch-needs-more-drag-lessons-on-presentation-from-drag-queens-d40e8d74e99a>
- Dolan, E., (2023). Psychological Resilience: Drag performers find strength in creativity and community, study suggests. <https://www.psypost.org/psychological-resilience-drag-performers-find-strength-in-creativity-and-community-study-suggests/>
- Elemia, C., (2024) Drag Goes Mainstream in the Philippines, a Bastion of Christianity <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/06/22/world/asia/drag-popular-philippines.html>
- Feldman, Z., Hakim, J., (2020) From Paris is Burning to #dragrace: social media and the celebrification of drag culture, *Celebrity Studies*, DOI:10.1080/19392397.2020.176508 <https://sci-hub.se/https://doi.org/10.1080/19392397.2020.176508>
- Fetters, M. D., & Tajima, C. (2022). Joint Displays of Integrated Data Collection in Mixed Methods Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069221104564> <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/16094069221104564>
- Garcia, Z., (2023). The Extraordinary Drag Culture. <https://opinyon.net/national/the-extraordinary-drag-culture>
- Gavrila, B., (2020). What do Ballroom and Latin Dancers and Drag Queens have in common? <https://dancesportlife.com/blog/performance/dancers-drag-queens/>
- Gazi, A., (2023). The Power of Drag: Celebrating The Art and Performance of Drag Queens and Kings.

<https://www.herzindagi.com/society-culture/celebrating-drag-culture-drag-kings-drag-queens-article-234483>

GLADD (2023). Updated Report: Drag Events Faced More than 160 Protests and Significant Threats Since Early 2022. <https://glaad.org/anti-drag-report/>

Gotinga, J., (2020). One more try: Hontiveros sponsors SOGIE equality bill in Senate plenary <https://www.rappler.com/nation/hontiveros-again-sponsors-sogie-equality-bill-senate-plenary/>

Gruberg, S., Mahowald, L., Halpin J., (2020) The State of the LGBTQ Community in 2020. <https://www.americanprogress.org/article/state-lgbtq-community-2020/>

Guynn, J., (2023). Google backs off LGBTQ drag show after complaints from Christian employees. <https://www.usatoday.com/story/tech/news/2023/06/27/google-drag-show-christian-employee-complaints/70362823007/>

Hapal, D., (2023). PRIDE and Prejudice Lies Hound the Philippines' Queer Anti-Discrimination Bill. <https://pulitzercenter.org/projects/pride-and-prejudice-lies-hound-philippines-queer-anti-discrimination-bill>

Hernandez, J., (2023). Visayas and Mindanao's drag queens: Behind their vibrant acts lie many challenges <https://www.rappler.com/life-and-style/arts-culture/visayas-mindanao-drag-queens-vibrant-acts-journeys-challenges/>

Huff, C., (2021) Queer subculture in the conservative south: A study of drag performers in Mississippi. <https://egrove.olemiss.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3012&context=etd>

Hunt, R., (2023). The Cultural Significance of Drag: A Look at How Drag Has Transformed and Influenced LGBTQIA+ Culture. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/cultural-significance-drag-look-how-has-transformed-robyn-hunt->

Joplin, K., (2023). The opulence of Manila Luzon. <https://www.japantimes.co.jp/culture/2023/12/10/stage/manila-luzon-japan-opulence-drag-queen-show/>

Lockwood, J., (2023) FAQ: What is Intersectionality Theory? <https://seechangehappen.co.uk/faq-what-is-intersectionality-theory/>

Kelly, C., Kasperavicius, D., Duncan, D. et al. 'Doing' or 'using' intersectionality? Opportunities and challenges in incorporating intersectionality into knowledge translation theory and practice. *Int J Equity Health* 20, 187 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-021-01509-z> <https://equityhealthj.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12939-021-01509-z#citeas>

Kaniuka, A., Berto K., Jordan, M., Brooks, B., Dood, J., Mann, A., Williams, S., Hirsch, J., (2019) Stigma and suicide risk among the LGBTQ population: Are anxiety and depression to blame and can connectedness to the LGBTQ community help? DOI: 10.1080/19359705.2018.1560385

Knutson, D., Flynn, K., Koch J, Paralvar, U., (2019) DOI: 10.1080/00918369.2019.1705669 <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338093124>

Kort, J (2023). Silence of the Trans. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/understanding-the-erotic-code/202304/silence-of-the-trans>

Loon, C., (2023). Commentary: Celebrating Drag as Art. <https://theaggie.org/2023/04/07/commentary-celebrating-drag-as-art/>

Madanguit, H., (2021). THE FIGHT FOR EQUALITY: The Advancement of SOGIE Equality Bill in the Philippines DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.25467.85289 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351905235THEFIGHTFOREQUALITY_TheAdvancementofSOGIEEqualityBillinthePhilippines

Madrangca, H., (2021). The Drag Race Phenomenon and its cultural effects on Filipino Drag subculture <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359921730TheDragRacePhenomenonanditsculturaleffectsonFilipinoDragSubculture/related>

McCormack, M., & Wignall, L., (2021). Drag Performers' Perspectives on the Mainstreaming of British Drag: Towards a Sociology of Contemporary Drag <https://doi.org/10.1177/00380385211008387> <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/00380385211008387#body-ref-bibr2-00380385211008387>

Marras, J., (2021). The Alchemy of Drag: Gender Fluidity and the Coniunctio Pacifica Graduate Institute ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, 2021. 28323166. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/937066643cfd09b3aa95b1fc16f4906f/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>

Marshall, A., (2023). Despite protests and threats, these Cleveland drag performers aren't backing down. <https://www.ideastream.org/race-gender-identity/202306-22>

McCormack, M., Wignall, L., (2021) Drag Performers' Perspective on the Mainstreaming of British Drag: Towards a Sociology of Contemporary Drag <https://doi.org/10.1177/00380385211008387> <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/00380385211008387>

- McLean Hospital (2023). Understanding the LGBTQ+ Mental Health <https://www.mcleanhospital.org/essential/lgbtq-mh#>
- Moon, D., & Burke, K., (2023) The Deep-Down Truth of Why Evangelical Christians Can't Stand Drag <https://slate.com/human-interest/2023/04/evangelical-drag-bills-theology.html>
- National Institutes of Health (2022). Emotional Wellness Toolkit <https://www.nih.gov/health-information/emotional-wellness-toolkit>
- Nikolopoulou, K., (2023), What is Snowball Sampling? Definition & Examples <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/snowball-sampling/>
- Njoroge, S., (2021). What is a Drag Queen. <https://www.lgbtqandall.com/what-is-a-drag-queen/>
- Olsen, B., (2023). The History of Drag. <https://www.lgbtqandall.com/the-history-of-drag/>
- Parincu, Z., (2023). Self-Growth: Definition, Examples, & Tips <https://www.berkeleywellbeing.com/self-growth.html>
- Razali, F., Aziz, N., Rasli, R., Zulkefly, N., Salim, S., (2019) Using Convergent Parallel Design Mixed Method to Assess the Usage of Multi-Touch Hand Gestures Towards Fine Motor Skills Among Pre-School Children <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBSS/v9-i14/7023>.
- Ricana, M., Giron, M., & Caletina, M., (2022). Untucking the popularity of Drag Race Philippines by the numbers. <https://www.rappler.com/entertainment/series/numbers-charts-untucking-popularity-drag-race-philippines/>
- Riopel, L., (2019) What is the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule? (PANAS) <https://positivepsychology.com/positive-and-negative-affect-schedule-panas/>
- Samonte, J., (2023). We Asked 3 Filipino Queens What they think about Drag Bans Happening. <https://mega-onemega.com/we-asked-3-filipino-queens-what-they-think-about-the-drag-bans-happening/>
- Shelton, L., (2022). Understanding the Joy of Life. <https://www.mindpath.com/resource/understanding-the-joy-of-drag/>
- Soubosky, N. (2021). Drag as a Method of Expressive Art Therapy For LGBT+ Individuals. Expressive Therapies Capstone Theses. 519. https://digitalcommons.lesley.edu/expressive_theses/519
- Sunstar Publishing Inc. (2023) Drag queen leads fight against HIV stigma <https://www.sunstar.com.ph/cebu/lifestyle/drag-queen-leads-fight-against-hiv-stigma>
- Tatler Philippines (2022). SOGIE Equality Bill: Everything You Need To Know— Supporters, Origins, And More. <https://www.tatlerasia.com/lifestyle/arts/pride-month-2021-sogie-equality-bill-timeline>
- Trevor Project (2022). The Trevor Project 2022 National Survey on LGBTQ Youth Mental Health <https://www.thetrevorproject.org/survey-2022/>
- Vasquez, C., (2023). Drag is MANY things...a Crime is Not One. <https://www.nelrights.org/drag-is-many-things-a-crime-is-not-one/>
- Venkatraman, R., Ozanne, J., & Coslor, E., (2024). Stigma Resistance through Body-in-Practice: Embodying Pride through Creative Mastery, Journal of Consumer Research, 2024;, ucae015, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcr/ucae015>. <https://academic.oup.com/jcr/advancearticle/doi/10.1093/jcr/ucae015/7611652>
- Vochelet, R., (2023) Philippines LGBTQ Activists Protest Arrest of Drag Artists <https://thediplomat.com/2023/10/philippines-lgbtq-activists-protest-arrest-of-drag-artist/>
- Vorobjovas-Pinta, O. & Hardy, A. (2021). Resisting Marginalisation and Reconstituting Space through LGBTQI+ Events. Journal of Sustainable Tourism, 29(2-3), 447-465. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1769638>.
- Wade, D., (2024). What is emotional health and well-being <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/emotional-wellbeing>
- Wallace, C., (2023) The Importance of Drag Queens <https://myresourcecenter.org/the-importance-of-drag-queens/>
- Weiner, E., (2022) Lessons Taught and Learned Through the Art of Drag. <https://www.adweek.com/brand-marketing/lesson>
- “The Importance of Drag Queens” (2023) <https://myresourcecenter.org/the-importance-of-drag-queens/>
- Watson, D., Clark, L.A., & Tellegen, A., (1988). From "Development and validation of brief measures of positive and negative affect: The PANAS scales. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 54, 1063-1070. Copyright (C) 1988 by the American Psychological Association. Reproduced with permission.

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